

OVARIAN CANCER ARISES OF HOW THE ENVIRONMENT OF THE COMING OF WOMEN?

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ABSTRACT

Ovarian cancer in the abdomen and in the pelvic bone, it does not determine many tarqalguncha xolni. This last stage in the treatment of ovarian cancer is more difficult. Successful treatment of ovarian cancer with disease limited to the ovaries only the initial stage. In the cure of cancer of the ovaries and chemical therapy is usually an estimation is used.

Cancer begins when cells in the body began to grow unattended. Only tumors that develops in the ovaries mali look than what the initial thought, but as recent research shows, most ovarian cancer starts in the cells of the distal tip of the fallopian tubes. Cancer cells rapidly multiply, to kill and to infiltratsiya has the feature to healthy tissue. The size of each almond as ovaries, as well as esterogen, and that is the production of progesterone garmon. This is a cancer which begins on the outer surface of the ovary-epiteliy the cell. In such species, cancer, and cancer can be partial. Epiteliy karsinomalari cancer tumors is called. Mali ovarian cancer, what to 85% from 90% to make up epithelial ovarian karsinomasi. 1-level karsinomalari is similar to more simple epithelial ovarian tissue. 3-level overhanging epithelial ovarian karsinomalari is dangerous.

1-type tumors grow slowly and occur with less characters. 1-level cell karsinomalarga crisp, slimy and endometrioid karsinomalar example. 2-type tumors grow quickly and spread rapidly. These tumors are more resistant to chemotherapy, the 3-level to the tumor carcinoma is an example. During the initial period of ovarian cancer without any symptoms may arise. When you start to occur with symptoms of other diseases, the symptoms of ovarian cancer are misleading.

Symptoms of ovarian cancer:

Tumor in the abdominal cavity;

Get a quick sense of nutrition;

Lose weight;

Low back pain;

Fatigue;

Pelvis pain(previously pain has not been realized)

Frequent urination.

According to the opinion of experienced doctors, ovarian cancer develops when dna changes in the ovaries. The rapid increase of the cells leads to the development of the changes and, as a result, cancer is a mass is formed. Ovarian cancer hereditary can be passed from the parents part. That increase the risk of ovarian cancer include brca1 and brca2 gene. This increases the risk of breast cancer genes and. Linch ovarian cancer syndrome, which produces a number of reasons, BR1PI, RAD51C and RAD51D gene consists of. The diagnosis of ovarian cancer for the next pelvic examination, imaging boaz test, blood check, and genetic tests should conduct an estimation of the mean ca125 test. There are a number of methods of treatment of ovarian cancer. Them that Car T-cell therapy comes into being at the expense of a new innovation. This therapy at the stage of high standing, has dedicated her new life to the patient. Developed by organisms receptor t cells (Car-T) therapy is called. Car-T therapy in CD-19 positive in the treatment of tumors has shown great efficiency what gemotologik mali.

Fair 227 of the risk of ovarian cancer in women 1yoki disease, or approximately 0.4%. In the period from about the age of 40 68 1 or under the age of 50 the risk of 1.5%. From the age of 60 increases the risk of the spread of the disease under the age of 70, will be 1 or 28, 3,6% is equal to. Who is the south african white women high extimoli to occur in Spanish, then Latin and south african black of them are women. Epithelial tumors are the most common type. Ovarian cancer is 85% from the top with the same type is common. The rating of the death of ovarian cancer in american women 5-stands in place. Each of the 78 women from ovarian cancer 1tasiga the diagnosis is put. The average age of diagnosis of ovarian cancer at the age of 63. Only 15% of diseases is the early diagnosis of ovarian cancer in the kingdom. Suffering from cancer early in women who are 5-year survival rate of 92% is equal to. 3-level women who are suffering from disease during the 5-year survival rate of 47% is equal to. In the year 2018 22240 the diagnosis of the disease in the country is put to the women of ovarian cancer. 16780 them (75,45%) 1-level disease tashxislangan. 5460 them (24,55%) 3-level disease tashxislangan. 14070 one patient died. 2020-almost at the end of the year put the diagnosis of ovarian cancer in women with ovarian cancer 23000 diagnosis of slowly lower the indicators of the last 20 years is gone, but this still stand in 5th place among the diseases which caused cancer death for women of reproductive organs cancer for women and is the second largest in.

If you established the diagnosis of ovarian cancer, treatment it is important for children to see. Probably, this include any operation that is combined with chemotherapy.the cancer is still contained in the lymph nodes surrounding the ovaries or ovarian cancer treatment in the initial stage will be much more effective. Many in the early detection of the disease, so good. An estimation of chemical therapy and is one of the best ways which will help you to prevent the return of cancer. September - in the fight against cancer of the ovaries, is the best time to get more information about the disease. Around the world, the fight against ovarian cancer day 8 may, but should be kurasish against cancer of the ovaries during the whole year. Every year on ovarian cancer leads to the death of close to 14000. In the meantime, according to the national cancer institute, the survival rate at one stage as 92.6% local% accounted for, that is, will determine where the cancer is still in the structure of the ovaries. After the cancer has spread to the regional lymph nodes also, stay alive 74,8 level to make up. Indeed, only 16% in cases of localized states and in 21% of the regional states will

hold. Therefore, know the symptoms of ovarian cancer and said to them, if anything happened to you, it is very important to talk with your medical care provider. Having a family history of brca1 or brca2 gene mutation or the age of 40 women with a high risk of having some after surgery to remove the ovaries and fallopian tubes may be recommended. Of the disease, and eastern european ashkenazi jews has to come out.

Scientists at the university of chicago medicine, in the year of the survey conducted 2019 Lengyel romero and ovarian cancer showing that metformin diabetes drug could be called to stop the spread of cancer cells in active interaction to reduce metabolitik eshi open to new test. Later, romero and ovarian cancer cells and fat cells Lengyel(adipotsitlar) can determine the set of relations. Other fats in fat cells, which release reception of the signal, the cancer cells fast allows it to operate as a source of energy for growth. This oil they stop the growth and spread of cancer cells by controlling the absorption of ovarian cancer toxtata is a method assumed that much. With the consolidation of researches have been conducted on ovarian cancer cells, researchers ebi another fatty acids which bind protein (FABP4), and will identify the metabolic purpose. Labaratoriya tests has shown that FABP4 to block metastatic ovarian cancer cells through will die of starvation. This ovarian cancer if the growth slows significantly. As a result, the slopes of fabp4 inhibitors are tested in conjunction with the standard treatment of ovarian cancer with the results replicated.

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